

INTEGRATING NANOTECHNOLOGY WITH BHASMAS IN PANCHAKARMA

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Nanotechnology is the science which deals with nanoparticles sized 1 to 100nm. This area focuses on designing future medicines with improved bioavailability and reduced toxicity by converting metals and minerals into nanoparticles (*Bhasmas*). The nanoparticles of *Bhasmas* which are the end products of minerals and metals, are having increased absorption with quick action rate & therapeutically efficient. Nanotechnology holds the potential to significantly enhance the efficacy, safety, and reach of Ayurvedic treatments, including Panchakarma, by addressing some of the inherent challenges of traditional Ayurvedic medicine. **Materials & Methods:** Panchakarma includes *Poorvakarma*, *Pradhana karma* and *Paschat karma*. From *Poorvakarma* till *Paschat karma* these *Bhasmas* plays a key role such as Administration of *Sneha* with *Kasisa Bhasma* as *Prakshepaka Dravya*, Practice of *Swedana karma* with *Bhasma*,

Virechana with *Ichhabhedi ras*, *Lekhana* type of *vasti* with *Ushakadi gana* for the management of *Medo roga*, *Uttara basti* with *Ghrita* and *Shilajatu Bhasma* in *Mutrakricchra*, *Dhooma nasya* with *Smritisagara rasa* in *Kaphavruta Pakshaghata*, *Rasayana Karma* using *Swarna Bhasma* provides remarkable results in clinical practice. **Discussion:** The impact of this nanotechnology integrated ayurvedic treatments mainly focuses on enhancing the efficacy of the treatment by targeted drug delivery system with improved stability, shelf life

& potential benefits. **Conclusion:** In conclusion, nanotechnology has the potential to revolutionize Ayurvedic Panchakarma. However, further research and rigorous safety evaluation are crucial to ensure its responsible and effective integration into this ancient system of medicine.

KEYWORDS: *bhasma*, nanotechnology, panchakarma.

INTRODUCTION

Ayurveda is an ancient system of Indian medicine, with therapeutic practices built on herbal, mineral and metallic preparations. Among these, *Bhasmas* - the incinerated metallic and mineral, herbal powders are having higher therapeutic efficiency but are a taboo in clinical practice. Nanotechnology is the area of science which focuses on conversion of metals and minerals, herbals into nanoparticles (*Bhasmas*) which are more absorbable, therapeutically effective and also having better absorption with targeted delivery. This technology holds the potential to significantly enhance the efficacy, safety and reach of ayurvedic treatments including *Panchakarma*. This article explores the concept of integrating nanotechnology with *bhasmas* and the advanced Ayurvedic therapeutic procedures known as *Panchakarma*.

MATERIALS METHODS

The *Bhasmas* have a key roles in our lives right from the childhood till ageing. These *Bhasmas* are usually prescribed with several other medicines in clinical practice for their quick absorption and immediate action. This particular phenomenon can be adopted in *Panchakarma* practice from preliminary to final stage. The preliminary stage of *Panchakarma* includes *Deepana – Pachana, Snehana and Swedana*.

Deepana – Pachana

Deepana – Pachana are the initial stage of *Poorva karma* which helps in correcting the digestive fire and does *Ama Pachana*. Some of the *Bhasmas* which are appetising and improves digestion are enlisted below. These can be used along with combination of other drugs for better results.

1. *Godanti Bhasma*
2. *Sambhuka Bhasma*
3. *Yava kshara + Jeeraka churna + Trikatu churna*
4. *Sarja kshara + Jeeraka churna + Pippali churna*
5. *Agnitundi vati*

Snehana

Snehana is an important *Poorvakarma* to perform *Shodhana* and it is of 2 types usually i.e., *Abhyantara Snehapanam* and *Bahya snehanam* (*Abhyanga, Samvahana, Mardana*). *Bhasmas* are mentioned for both internal and external use which are usually in combination with herbal drugs.

1. *Sidhma Kusta* – External application of *Yava Kshara + Tila taila*.
2. *Pandu – Loha Bhasma / Vanga Bhasma + ghrita - Snehapanam* daily.
3. *Gulma, Atisara – Tamra Bhasma + Trikatu churnam + Ghrita - Snehapanam* daily.
4. *Vataja Gulma – Sarja Kshara + Kusta churna+ Ketaki kshara + Tila taila – Snehapanam* daily.
5. *Rakta Gulma – Palasa kshara jala + Murchita Sneha – Snehapanam* daily.

Swedana

Swedana is one of the importance *Poorvakarma* usually performed after *Snehana* which helps in *Dosha vilayanam* (Liquefaction). *Bhasmas* of animal origin i.e., *Gomaya Bhasma* (cow dung) is made into a *Pottali* and performed as *Swedana karma* in cases of *Medoroga* (Obesity) and have shown significant results in reduction of weight.

Vamana

Vamana Karma is one of the important and first *Pradhana Karma* which helps in elimination of *Kapha dosha* and *Kapha samsrusta dosa* through oral route. Though *Bhasmas* are not directly anywhere involved in performing *Vamana*, there are references that proves its involving. *Tanka Bhasma* is helpful in *Vamanopaga* action. *Tutta + Madanaphala* can be administered as *Vamaka Dravya*.

Virechana

Virechana is one of the *pancha Shodhana* and helps in eliminating vitiated and apakwa *Pitta dosha* and *Vata Anulomana*. *Nitya Shodhana* is a type of *Virechana*, which doshas are eliminated in small amounts on regular basis.

1. *Arshas – Haratala Bhasma + Haritaki Churnam – Nithya Shodhana*
2. *Udara roga – Tanka Bhasma + Trikatu Churna + Jayapala Churnam - Mridu Virechana*
3. *Ichhabhedhi Rasa – Virechana*.

Basti

Basti is considered as *Ardha chikitsa*. It is beneficial in *Vatadi rogas*. There are 3 types of *Basti* i.e., *Asthapana Basti*, *Anuvasana Basti* and *Uttara Basti*. *Bhasmas* that are used as *Avapa Dravya* can be helpful in providing desired outcome of treatment.

1. *Lekhana Basti* – *Ushakadi gana (Kasisa, Hingu, Tuttha, Ushaka etc.,)* - *Medoroga, Mutrakricchra*
2. *Niruha Basti using Suddha Sphatika + jala* - *Guda Bhramsha, Arshas*
3. *Erandamooladi Niruha Basti* – *Rasanjana* is one of the ingredients.
4. *Dwipanchamooladya yapana Basti, Koshatakaadi Basti, Kshara Basti, Patoladi Niruha Basti* – *Yava Kshara*.
5. *Uttara Basti* – *Suddha Sphatika + Cow's milk* – *Meha vrana, Puya srava*.
6. *Uttara Basti* – *Gomutra Sadhitha Shilajatu + Kalyanaka Ghrita* in Kalmann's Syndrome.
7. *Yoni Basti with Sphatika + water* – Helps in reinstate uterus in its normal position.
8. *Abhraka Bhasma* can be used as adjuvant in *Uttara Basti* for *Mutrakricchra roga*.

Nasya

Nasya is one of the *Panchakarma* performed in *Shodhana in Uttamanga or Urdhwa jatru rogas*, where the medicine is installed through nose and thus helps in elimination of the *Doshas*.

Bhasmas can be used in *Dhuma* type of *Nasya* in different types of diseases.

1. *Nasya with Yashada Bhasma + Ghee* – Allergic Rhinitis.
2. *Nasya with Shuddha Sphatika + Cow's milk* – Prevents Nasal Bleeding.
3. *Nasya with Smritisagara rasa + Haridradi Dhuma varti* – *Kaphavruta Pakshaghata*.

Rasayana

Rasayana and Vajeekarana are the *Paschat Karma* performed after *Shodhana Karma* performed to prevent further recurrence of the disease, promotion of health by increasing the immune power. *Bhasmas* have a key role in *Rasayana karma* as well. *Swarna Bhasma* acts as *Rasayana* and *Vrishya* as well. *Swarna Prashana* is a part of one of the *Shodasha Samskara*, where *Swarna Bhasma* along with honey is administered to kids from 6 years - 16 years to improve immunity, health booster and prevents diseases.

DISCUSSION

The preparation of *Bhasmas* is a complex process that transforms heavy metals and toxic

minerals into biocompatible, therapeutically active nanoparticles. Techniques like *Shodhana* (purification) and *Marana* (incineration and wet grinding) involve repeatedly heating the material with herbal juices or extracts.

Nanotechnology could impact *Ayurvedic Panchakarma* by enhancing the bioavailability and efficacy with targeted drug delivery and reduced side effects. It helps in improved stability and shelf life. Adopting green nanotechnology approaches in the manufacturing of ayurvedic medicines can contribute to a more controlled, scalable and environmentally friendly production process. Implication of *Bhasmas* in each of the stage adds a remarkable impact and helps in quick relief. *Bhasmas* helps in targeted lipid based nanocarriers and create Nano emulsions to penetrate deeper into tissues and thus helps in eliminating the vitiated *Doshas*. In *Basti*, they helps in absorption of active ingredients through the colon, thus improving their therapeutic effects on various systemic diseases. The olfactory system has a direct pathway to the CNS (*Nasahi Shiraso Dwaaram*). Thus *Bhasma* helps in delivering the medicine with greater precision, proving beneficial for treating neurological and respiratory disorders.

CONCLUSION

The synergy between *Ayurvedic Panchakarma* and modern nanotechnology offers a promising frontier for therapeutic innovation. The targeted action of *Bhasmas* plays a key role in delivering the medicine to the disease specific pathological sites, minimizing systemic side effects and maximizing therapeutic outcomes. In conclusion, nanotechnology has the potential to revolutionize *Ayurvedic Panchakarma*. However, further research and rigorous safety evaluation are crucial to ensure its responsible and effective integration into this ancient system of medicine.

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